

**THE INTERPRETATION OF THE RAVISH SERIES IN
UZBEK LANGUAGE EXPLANATORY DICTIONARIES**

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Annotation . Ravish is Uzbek language of grammar important piece is considered This of the ravish category in the article explanatory in our dictionaries interpretation , morphological aspects discussion will be done .

Key words : word _ category , approach, grammar , method .

INTRODUCTION

Ravishkari the character , in particular , of the action symbol expression reach feature and this in progress characters gradually show of opportunity existence of this as a result to the body came synonymous options and inter-style functional limitations this word The series is also methodological possibilities enough level from being proof will give . Ravishkari not changing his in use methodical diversity to be limits . With that together , their speech in the process normalization , stabilization makes it easier .

LITERATURE REVIEW

-Dictionary of the Uzbek language || _____ (5 vol .) _____
___ groups according to classification is as follows:

1. Adverbs: *forever, eternally, foolishly, at the peak, clearly like that diligently exactly, in particular ayro vice versa, on the contrary otherwise, mind fuck hustle and bustle apil-tapil, apir-shapir, barely cheap bail, not at all mainly, slowly, gradually, gradually , asti, around bajo, bazoor, baloday, bamaylhotir, bara, baraiga, barilla, basma-bas, hello worse, bathroom, estimated appraiser, well done shameless missing stupid bedam-tree, badass without exception in vain out of turn good life back little by little chapanis slowly chaparasta, chappa, chappasiga, bucket, click, clickgradually _ friends...*

2. Place recipes : *since _ beyond , beyond , in the middle inside _ outside _ in front behind* such as .

3. Time recipes : *forever _ first , first of all first of all in the past long ago immediately _ in prayer easily _ already _ aloha(l), occasionally _ early _ sometimes _ _ sometimes _ useless , immediately _ first , initially , until _ always ...*

1. Reason recipes : *helpless , almost ...*

2. The goal recipes : *daddy _ on purpose on purpose on purpose on purpose ...*

3. Level-quantity adjectives : *most , most , much , much , almost _ worldly _ _ like ...*

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

In the dictionary first the way with formed the following words explanation too given : *first of all first of all previous , as before before , first , at first first of all ¹.*

Few ravishi too one how many meaning no to the edge has :

¹ Uzbek of the language glossary.- _ Tashkent , 2020. - 5 volume. . Volume 1. – B.30

<i>Few</i>		
<p>1 Son or amount in terms of so much a lot did not happen; less Few time There is little water in the pool. A lot of wood, little coal. Proverb. Few food — soz food Proverb. Recently I showed the doctors you have low blood we are drink said. A.Qadiri, Past days.</p>	<p>2 Enough it's not, enough does not satisfactory did not happen; less One Seventy skills are not enough for a young man. Proverb. don't brag goose your skill is small. Proverb. A lotif — leaves little if — enough Proverb. Both of us who spend gold of your life gold minutes each how much gold hour date little! A. Cairo, Pain teeth. Electric power that's it until little that was pump motors to convert too weakness</p>	<p>3 rvsh. Sometimes; occasionally rarely. Anwar is the same age with little contact does to them less interfere and Ortish don't play and laugh was A. Qadiri, From the altar scorpion Nuri to their hut when she was a girl it was very little. Oybek, Chosen works. a little a little like A little there is little salt. Aunt Robia a little until bent, with small steps whispering to the platform road started S. Zunnunova, Fire. A lot gone little left From half a lot gone from him a small amount left (difficulty days, hard work, etc. about). - Many are gone, little left — washed him Osmanjon, — never thing it's not, this difficulties past</p>

Repetitive in ravishes too polysemy observed .

<i>PIECE BY PIECE</i>		
<p>1. Particles, separated into grains, each grain is separate. Fine teeth. Incense pieces and pieces, Let the room be filled with smoke. "Boypox". of the sprout There are pieces with holes side by side. "Yusuf and Ahmad".</p>	<p>2. rvsh. vzf. One by one, one by one; piecemeal I plucked flowers piece by piece. "Folklore". He wiped the tears falling from his eyes with a white handkerchief and answered in a trembling voice. Sh. Rashidov, stronger than the storm.</p>	<p>3. rvsh. mobile Clear, clear, understandable. Jorakhan answered the writer's questions piece by piece. Nazarmat, Djorlar dances high. Mutrib took a piece of paper rolled into a tube from under the pillow and began to read it piece by piece with a beautiful recitation. S. Siyoyev, Light. The addresses of the buildings were written in large letters on a sheet of checkered paper torn from the side notebook. M. Khairullayev, Tilla necklace.</p>

In the explanatory dictionary, the first meaning of this word belongs to which category not shown. Second and third entry into the category of ravish with its meaning shown ².

² Uzbek of the language explanatory dictionary . - Tashkent , 2020. – 5 volumes . Volume 1. - B.643.

Or :

OBVIOUSLY		
1 Clearly, undoubtedly. This is an outright slander. In fact, her [Zainab's] affair was clearly childish. A. Kadiri, Past days.	2 Open, demonstrative; frankly. Openly oppose. This sneer directed at Akbarov made Zufar Hakimovich very angry. P. Kadyrov, Three roots.	3 Without beating, without praying, without being ashamed. Swear openly.

Some adjectives certain meaning with ravish on duty coming can be seen from the descriptions in the explanatory dictionary. For example, a soul with many meanings the word only only one meaning with ravish on duty will come that shown:

JOHN

1. Low variety , quality low, poor quality John mol. mm Makhдум thinking remained: - If not, - he said hesitantly, - take it from a better address! A. Qadiri, A scorpion from the altar.

2. Portable Privileged to class belongs to did not happen ; simple , simple _ [Yusufbek pilgrim :] John people in line man kill I walked say ?! — said . -John people in line it's not , — said [Otabek], — forced among the those who were raped among the ! A. Qadiri , Past days _

3. Low level , empty , weak . John work _ The last one page livelier written it is A. Cairo , A mirage . Yesterday high art example

being seen work today to our eyes soul being it seems "East star".Some the press organs progressives experience superficially soul they are writing.From the newspaper.

4. So much complicated and difficult did not happen ; easy , light . Mahfuza Plumber in the district 9-children to the hospital to work entered _ The task very soul : each day three - four place ready foods chamber-chamber walking distributes . From the newspaper .Work this oil soul moved . H. Ghulam , Tashkent people .

5 rvsh. vzf. void, simply; to idleness have fun by doing In the village soul instead of walking, we bought a balloon for ourselves. "Ochildov". Saidi is like that he couldn't do it, because he was tired not only by reading, but also by leafing through the book. A. Angry, A mirage.

4. 3-sh. ownership and j. k., Ch. k. additions with grave vzf. is used (for from the soul) ³. Before the way too polysemantic:

³ Uzbek of the language explanatory dictionary . - Tashkent , 2020. – 5 volumes . Volume 1. - B.117.

BEFORE		
1 radish. In front, in front; before. He is before me. Stand in front. At that moment, the bus carrying passengers stopped. S. Zunnunova, Fire.	2 Initially, firstly. Before being afraid raise a fist. Proverb. It is new that he went there before everyone else it was natural for the teachers themselves to be ashamed. P. Tursun, Teacher.	3 Initially, firstly. He raises his fist before he is afraid. Proverb. First of all, the new teachers are ashamed of themselves it was natural. P. Tursun, Teacher.

Before the word with surface came one series words in the dictionary explanation found _ These are : *forward* _____ *then , back and forth , back and forth , back and forth* .

Easily the way too polysemantic :

EASILY	
1 Ease with, a lot strength, work without spending; easily _ effortless. Achievements are easy hand did not enter This problem easily ending the work it wasn't. "Youth". Ghulamkadir's sing very miss the rest If he doesn't sing a couple of songs, it's from us easily can't escape. M. Ismaili, Fergana until	2 Resistance without showing. Khalkozi knows Zumrad. He is an easy soul not of women who give. S. Siyoyev, Horseman a woman Ours in the village big land owners easily soul that he gave no A. Cairo, Koshchinor lights.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

1. Ravishes another all independent word categories such as big methodical to opportunities have _ Because of the the character , in particular , of the action symbol expression reach feature and this in progress characters gradually show of opportunity existence , of this as a result to the body came synonymous options and inter-style functional limitations this word of the series too methodical possibilities enough level from being proof will give .

2. -Uzbek ek __ language i n i n g i z o h l i l u g a t i || (5 j i l d l i) n i n g m a ' l u m one short m i n i r a v i s h s organize does _ In the dictionary single , double and repeated in the form of pure imitative and descriptive 2000 words _ near be this common 2.5 of the number per cent that's right will come . That's it with together _ FIRE at sign not specified ravishes too occurs .

Uzbek in the language there is of ravishes some of them explanatory to the dictionary not included . In some ravish sign not put

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